

EMBEDDED WIRELESS SENSORS IN COMPOSITE SHIP STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT: The goal of the present project is to develop a wireless system to monitor composite material ship hulls during sea operation in order to predict load levels and health. There are several incentives to develop such a system. Lately there has been an increase in the number of composite ships being built. These ships suffer from a number of non-traditional failure modes, including catastrophic peeling (skin/core debonding). There is currently no simple means to monitor the health of the hull between major inspections. Major inspections may be scheduled annually and often involve dry docking. For the extended period of time between inspections, widespread damage in load bearing structures remains unnoticed. The proposed solution is a system consisting of a large number of small embedded modules with data acquisition and wireless transmission capabilities, piezoelectric patches which harvest energy from the deforming ship hull to power the modules, and strain gages. Future systems may incorporate more sensors, such as accelerometers and temperature sensors. The present project has so far dealt with energy harvesting using piezoelectric materials, strength reduction of a sandwich structure due to the presence of the embedded modules and wireless transmission through carbon fiber skins.

KEYWORDS: embedded sensors, energy harvesting, health monitoring, piezoelectric, composite sandwich structures

INTRODUCTION

Load and health monitoring are important for safe operation as well as reduced inspection and maintenance costs of marine ship hulls made from composites. This is because a wide variety of defects such as delaminations, fiber and matrix cracks and skin-core debonds are difficult to detect but can have a detrimental effect on the strength and performance of the structure. Minor damage can quickly grow in fatigue and lead to major failures. An example of this is the fiberglass/foam core sandwich vessel JetRider. This ship lost large areas of skin laminate when initially small impact damage grew in fatigue to a critical size, after which a large part of the outer skin catastrophically peeled off. In order to reduce the risk of such accidents, it is crucial to have a large number of closely spaced sensors throughout a structure. In-service load and health monitoring and subsequent condition-based maintenance practice could replace fixed-service-time-interval inspections and maintenance.

This research investigates small modular data acquisition systems with wireless transmitters embedded in the core of composite skin sandwich structures. The presently considered sandwiches consist of two stiff and strong composite material skins (glass or carbon fiber reinforced plastics) on either side of a lightweight foam or balsa core. The vision is to eventually have thousands or even millions of modules embedded in critical structures,

continuously monitoring loads and structural health. The goal of this monitoring system is to autonomously measure the loads and health of the structure.

SYSTEM OVERVIEW

This embedded system has four components: sensors, data acquisition system, transmitter, and power supply. The sensors used in the prototype system are simple but reliable foil strain gages. Data acquisition and wireless transmission will be accomplished with small sugar cube sized wireless module. Piezoelectric materials will power the system. Embedded patches of piezoelectric material will deform with the ship structure and generate energy from its vibration and deformation.

Piezoelectric patches have successfully been used to generate power in other applications [1-4]. The use of piezoelectric patches to harvest energy from latent vibrations/deformations on structures has been investigated for this application, and has proved to be a viable power source. Both PVDF polymer film and PZT ceramic fiber piezoelectric materials have been studied for this application.

It is necessary that this health monitoring system not compromise the mechanical properties of the hull. The data acquisition and wireless transmission module is the thickest component of the embedded system and is thus expected to have the most impact on the strength of the structure. The effect of embedded wireless modules on structural strength has been investigated. The strain gage and the thin piezoelectric patch are expected to have less impact on the strength of the structure.

The data acquisition and wireless transmitter module is roughly the size of a sugar cube. This module enables recording and reporting the data acquired by embedded sensors without the use of wires. Transmission and power consumption are the primary challenges in using this module. Transmission is a challenge because carbon fiber skins create a Faraday cage that impedes the signal. Investigative tests have been done to show that transmission through carbon fiber skin is possible. Transmission is limited by power consumption. It takes much more power to transmit a signal, than to collect and process data. Ideally, some degree of data processing would take place prior to transmission in order to transmit a smaller amount of refined data and thus reduce power consumption.

HARVESTING ENERGY FROM DYNAMICALLY LOADED SANDWICH BEAMS

To investigate energy harvesting, a piezo patch (polymer film PVFT or ceramic fiber PZT), and a strain gage were attached to the surface of a small sandwich beam. This sandwich beam was made by infusing a Hexcel 7725 glass fiber skin, 2/2 twill weave cut at +/- 45°, 298 g/m², on either side of a H70 Divinycell foam core. The resulting beam was 42 x 25 x 620mm. Then, this sandwich beam was dynamically loaded in four-point bending. The test rig used is shown in figure 1. Frequency was controlled by a solenoid through LabView and the force was adjusted by the air pressure driving a pneumatic cylinder.

Figure 1 Four point bending test fixture with pneumatic cylinder.

Voltage from the deforming piezoelectric patches was measured and related to the strains in the beams. Tests at a range of displacement and frequency values were conducted for both PZT and PVDF. A sample of the recorded signal is shown in figure 2. From this data, a frequency response function was computed, based on the assumption that the relationship between the piezoelectric output and the strain input is linear. This frequency response function was developed using the following manipulation [5].

TRANSFER FUNCTION FROM CROSS CORRELATION

Assume that the input $x(t)$ is periodic with the period T . It may then be expanded in a Fourier series,

$$x(t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} A_k e^{i2\pi kt/T} \quad (1)$$

where A_k are complex constants. The output is assumed to be

$$y(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(\tau)x(t-\tau)d\tau \quad (2)$$

where $h(t) = y(t)$ for a unit impulse input (i.e., for $x(t) = \delta(t)$). For periodic input, the output is also periodic with the same frequency, and it may be expanded in a Fourier series,

$$y(t) = \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} B_l e^{i2\pi lt/T} \quad (3)$$

where B_l are complex constants. Let M be an integer and introduce the cross and auto correlations

$$r_{xy}(\tau) = \frac{1}{MT} \int_0^{MT} x(t)y(t+\tau)d\tau = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} A_k B_{-k} e^{-j2\pi k\tau/T} \quad (4)$$

$$r_{xx}(\tau) = \frac{1}{MT} \int_0^{MT} x(t)x(t+\tau)d\tau = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} A_k A_{-k} e^{-j2\pi k\tau/T}$$

which are also periodic in T . Introduce their spectral densities,

$$g_{xy}(f) = 2 \int_0^{MT} r_{xy}(\tau) e^{-j2\pi f\tau} d\tau = \begin{cases} 2MT A_k B_{-k} & \text{for } f = -k/T \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Figure 2 This is a sample of the data recorded from the dynamic four point bend test

$$g_{xx}(f) = 2 \int_0^{MT} r_{xx}(\tau) e^{-j2\pi f\tau} d\tau = \begin{cases} 2MTA_k A_{-k} & \text{for } f = -k/T \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Dividing these by each other with a minor rearrangement yields

$$\frac{g_{xy}(f)}{g_{xx}(f)} = \begin{cases} B_k/A_k & \text{for } f = k/T \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

which equals the frequency response function (B_k/A_k). The frequency response function could be calculated directly by expanding the input and output in Fourier series and dividing their respective coefficients. However, the use of the correlation functions is expected to significantly reduce the influence of noise. This was also the reason for using M periods rather than a single period. This method has provided the following frequency response function plots from experimental data shown in figure 3. It may be added that at these frequencies the common model of a piezoelectric consisting of an idea voltage source (whose output is proportional to straining) in series with a capacitor is not representative.

Figure 3(a) Plots A-D are for PZT ceramic. The left-hand plots are of amplitude, while the right hand plots are of phase angle. Plots A and B are for four different frequency values at the constant amplitude of 23 psi. Plots C and D are for a frequency of 5 Hz, at different displacement values corresponding to 20, 21, and 23 psi in the pneumatic cylinder that drives the deformation

Figure 3(b) Plots E-H are for PVDF polymer film. The left-hand plots are of amplitude, while the right hand plots are of phase angle. Plots E and F are for four different frequency values at the constant amplitude of 23 psi. Plots G and H are for a frequency of 5 Hz, at different displacement values corresponding to 20, 21, and 23 psi in the pneumatic cylinder that drives the deformation.

REDUCTION OF STRENGTH DUE TO EMBEDDED MODULES

Experiments to assess the reduction of strength of the sandwich structure due to the embedded modules have been conducted. Sandwich beams representative of ship hulls in the 30 meter class were fabricated with and without embedded modules and tested to failure in four point bending.

MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURE OF BEAM WITH EMBEDDED MODULE

Glass fiber / vinyl ester skins were vacuum infused directly onto high density Divinycell foam cores. The beams were loaded in four point bending with the module under the compression loaded skin.

Figure 4 Four point bending test

Figure 4 shows the test of such a beam and Figure 5 shows the final failure. One wireless module

was embedded in the center of the sandwich beam and then tested on a four-point-bending fixture. Several sandwich beams of the same size, without embedded modules were also tested on the same four point bending test fixture. The test result shows that, although the location of the failure is different for the module embedded beams and the normal sandwich beams, the failure load is similar for the two kinds of beams.

The materials used in making the module-embedded sandwich beams were TH4000 ($0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$) from Saint-Gobain BTI, surface weight $1350\text{g}/\text{m}^2$ glass fiber, Divinycell HD250 foam core and Dow Derakane 8048 vinyl ester resin. Resin grooves and a rectangular hole were cut into on the Divinycell HD250 foam core. The rectangular hole was slightly bigger than the wireless module. The module was put inside the hole and then glued in place with Loctite Hysol 9430 and the surface was made level with the surface of the foam core. Two layers of the glass fiber reinforcement were placed on either side of the foam core, so that the $\pm 45^\circ$ side of the glass fiber faced the foam core. The 0° ply was in the length direction of the beam, which was also the resin diffusion direction. The entire layup was covered with peel ply and sealed in a vacuum bag. The resin was mixed according to Dow's specifications and degassed until the majority of the bubbles had vanished. The resin was then injected into the mold with the help of vacuum.

Once the resin had fully cured, the specimen was demolded and cut with a waterjet cutter into a beam 1000mm long, and 130mm wide, with the embedded module in the center. Several sandwich beams with no module were also made with the same procedure.

TESTING OF BEAMS WITH EMBEDDED MODULES

The four point bend testing was done on a MTI modified 10 kip Instron universal test machine. Tests were performed under displacement control. The crosshead rate was 5mm/min. Two sandwich beams with embedded modules were tested to failure, with the module on the compression side. Four reference beams with no embedded module were also tested to failure for comparison.

For the two module-embedded sandwich beams, the failure location was nearly at the center of the beam, at the edge of the module. For the first beam, the surface of the glass fiber skins over the embedded module were approximately 0.7mm lower than the beam surface. This small dip in the skins over the module caused failure of the beam earlier than expected, at 25.6kN. For the second beam, much care was given to embedding the module completely flush with the surface of the foam. This beam failed at 29.9kN with the glass fiber failure at the same location as the first beam.

Four comparison, sandwich beams without embedded modules were also tested to failure with the same test fixture. The failure mode for these four beams was also in the glass fiber. The location of the failure was near one of the inner supports of the test fixture. The critical force at failure ranged from 29.3kN to 34.4kN.

Figure 5 Failure of a beam with an embedded module

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION OF STRUCTURAL IMPACT DUE TO EMBEDDED COMPONENTS

The very limited data suggests that the embedded modules reduce the strength of the beams by approximately 8% when they are perfectly aligned with the top surface of the core before the composite skins are infused. However, if the modules are mounted approximately 0.7 mm below the top surface of the core, a very slight dip results in the composite skin right over the module. This small dip causes the strength to be drastically reduced. A reduction of more than 20% was measured.

The embedded components of the system including the wireless transmitter, the sensors, and the energy harvesting piezoelectrics, introduce geometric features with different material properties. These properties include elastic moduli, coefficients of thermal expansion, etc., which differ from the surrounding sandwich structure. Hence, they will have some effect on the mechanical behavior of the structure.

The thin piezoelectric film or patch attached to the core will likely be stronger than the core. Thus, in general, the core will be expected to fail before any failure in the piezoelectric occurs. The piezo film is also extremely thin, so no cavity will be needed to embed the patch, and the skins over the film should remain flat.

WIRELESS TRANSMISSION

Signal transmission is constrained by the small size and the small amount of power available to the transmitter. Since the trend is that advanced sandwich structures are using more carbon fibers, emphasis is placed on carbon fiber sandwich structures. Transmission and attenuation through carbon fiber skin sandwich structures have been tested. A carbon fiber box was made to conduct these tests. A transmitter with known orientation relative to an analyzer antenna transmitted a signal outside the box and the signal was measured. Then the same measurement was repeated, but with the transmitter inside the carbon was measured. Then, the same measurement was repeated, but with the transmitter inside the carbon fiber box. The opening of the box was closed using copper tape, thus preventing the signal from “leaking” out through the opening. The tests were performed with several different orientations at the same distance, using a 418 MHz transmitter (approximately 0 dBm output power). Attenuation was measured to 80+/-1dB.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Piezoelectrics were mounted on sandwich beams and dynamically loaded. The frequency response functions of a PVDF polymer film and a PZT ceramic fiber piezoelectrics were obtained for the frequency range believed to be of interest for ship structures. Data acquisition and wireless transmission modules were embedded in sandwich beams representative of ship structures and loaded to failure. The test results indicate that the strength is not overly affected if the modules are flush with the surface of the foam core. However, small deviations leading to waviness in the composites skins significantly reduced strength. Finally, a wireless transmitter was placed within a carbon fiber sandwich box and attenuation was measured. Initial results indicate that transmission through carbon fiber skins is possible, but the attenuation is very significant.

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